

WAQF FOR WATER: EXAMINING CONTRIBUTIONS AND SUPPORT TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS- A MALAYSIAN CASE STUDY

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 25 Dec 2024 Revised: 3 Jan 2024 Accepted: 25 Jan 2024 Published: 1 Feb 2024</p>	<p>Waqf played a significant historical role in facilitating infrastructure, education, healthcare, and other essential services within Islamic civilization. Waqf is a powerful instrument for mobilizing resources to address societal needs through the self-sustaining contributions of private donors rather than relying on governmental borrowing or the expenditure of tax funds. The issue of water scarcity is becoming increasingly critical for numerous countries. Currently, 2.4 billion people reside in countries facing water stress, a classification given to states that extract 25% or more of their renewable freshwater resources to fulfil their water needs. The United Nations has projected that an annual allocation of approximately \$27 billion will be required to ensure comprehensive access to water services and sanitation facilities by 2030. One of the incentives that can be implemented to address this issue is the introduction of waqf mechanisms. Waqf can be utilized as a potential means to assist economically limited Islamic communities, particularly in Islamic countries that face challenges in providing access to water services. This qualitatively descriptive study aims to delineate the potential of cash waqf in Malaysia as an instrument to address water-related issues, particularly financial financing. The research delves into Waqf as a mechanism for fundraising to channel assistance to Muslim communities lacking access to water. The discussion's outcomes reveal that Waqf can serve as a fundraising mechanism to meet the basic needs of Islamic communities unable to access such necessities. Simultaneously, it can offer an alternative for the government to implement waqf plans to aid the Muslim population in economically challenged Islamic countries.</p>
<p>Keywords: Waqf, Water, Cash Waqaf, Philanthropy, Sustainable Development Goals,</p> <p></p>	

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INTRODUCTION

Water scarcity is a critical issue for a growing number of countries. Today, 2.4 billion people live in water-stressed countries, defined as states that withdraw 25% or more of their renewable freshwater resources to meet demand (United Nations Environment Programme, 2024). Southern and Central Asia, as well as North Africa, have been particularly hard-struck. Even countries with highly developed infrastructure, such as the United States, are experiencing record-low water levels. Along with climate change, the situation is fueled by uncontrolled urbanization, rapid population expansion, pollution, and land development. Water scarcity has already impacted everything from food security to biodiversity, and it is expected to grow more widespread in the coming years. The availability of clean water has become an urgent necessity due to the increasing demand for water in agriculture, industry, and domestic use. Additionally, water scarcity and the inadequacy of sanitation facilities consistently pose global challenges and attract worldwide attention.

Currently, the world is facing a water crisis. An estimated 800,000 people die each year due to water insecurity, limited sanitation facilities, and poor lifestyle practices (United Nations, 2023). The World Bank (2014) report states that the current challenges for countries involve ensuring water supply and acquisition, which are significant and complex in the economic sector. The increasing population and rising economic growth have placed anticipated pressure on water demand. The findings also estimate that by 2030, based on current water usage practices, the world is facing a 40% deficit between water demand and supply.

According to the latest statistics in the United Nations' Global Issues report, over 3 billion people, constituting almost half of the world's population, live on less than US\$2.50 per day. Additionally, 640 million people lack adequate shelter, 925 million suffer from hunger, 400 million lack access to safe water, 270 million have no access to health services, 10.6 million die before reaching the age of 5, and 1 billion are illiterate. Hence, the imperative to implement funding instruments such as Waqf, aligned with the belief systems of contributors and needy communities, has never been more pronounced than it is now.

The increased financial requirements associated with water management in countries can be attributable to several complex reasons. Among these are the significant investments needed for the construction, maintenance, and improvement of water supply and sanitation infrastructure, which includes complex systems such as dams, treatment facilities, pipelines, and distribution networks. Furthermore, the adoption of sophisticated water treatment technologies, the mitigation of geographical challenges, population growth necessitating infrastructure expansion, and the need to protect water sources and ecosystems all contribute to the complex economic landscape that influences the high costs of water management.

Indeed, concerns such as energy costs, adherence to demanding water quality standards, adaptation measures in response to water scarcity caused by climate change, and governance-related administrative overheads further aggravate budgetary constraints. Islamic Finance and sustainable development naturally complement each other, driven by a shared purpose and common values. Specifically, philanthropic Islamic social finance tools like Waqf (endowment), sadaqah (voluntary donations), and zakat (mandatory almsgiving) are intentionally designed to address inequalities and uplift the most vulnerable populations. As a comprehensive faith, Islam offers a holistic framework that addresses various dimensions of human existence, including economic, social, political, and spiritual aspects, establishing a detailed code of conduct for its adherents (Hamidullah, 1973). To ensure economic and social equality, Islam mandates its followers to engage in both obligatory acts of charity, such as zakat, and voluntary acts, such as sadaqah and Waqf. These practices aim to address financial disparities and establish justice within the community (Hardiyanto et al., 2018).

Islamic economics, with its unique mechanism of waqaf (endowment), holds promising potential to contribute significantly to achieving Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly in water sanitation. Waqaf, deeply rooted in Islamic principles, involves the voluntary and perpetual dedication of specific assets to benefit the community. In water sanitation, the establishment of waqaf-funded initiatives could play a pivotal role in financing sustainable water projects. These waqaf funds can be utilized to build and maintain water treatment plants, construct sanitation facilities, and implement infrastructure projects that enhance access to clean water.

Waqf asset pools hold considerable value. According to (World Bank, International Centre for Education in Islamic Finance (INCEIF), & International Shari'ah Research Academy for Islamic Finance, 2019), the global valuation of waqf assets fell from USD 700 billion to USD 1 trillion. If efficiently utilized, Waqf can substantially contribute to narrowing the annual USD 2.5 trillion funding gap for the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

The perpetual nature of Waqf ensures a sustainable and ongoing source of funding, aligning with the long-term objectives of SDGs. Moreover, Waqf encourages community involvement and fosters a sense of social responsibility, creating a collaborative environment for addressing water sanitation challenges. By leveraging Islamic economic principles through Waqf, societies can establish a robust financial mechanism that supports SDGs and empowers communities to secure access to clean water and sanitation, promoting overall well-being and sustainable development.

To address this issue, the instrument or Implementation of Waqf must be further strengthened to enhance the country's economic development, particularly in developing our nation's water sector. In addition to Waqf, adequate mobilization of both sadaqah (charity) and zakat (almsgiving) has the potential to act as catalysts for achieving the SDGs

LITERATURE REVIEW

Waqf refers to a property in which the donor (waqif) retains ownership rights, preventing its transfer through transactions, inheritance, gifts, or wills while preserving its physical assets ('ain). The purpose of dedicating the property is to contribute to general or specific welfare, as prescribed, with the intention of drawing closer to Allah SWT through the act of Waqf.

The term "waqf" is derived from the Arabic term "waqf" or "awqaf" (plural), which translates to "withhold," "forbid," or "stop." Another synonymous term with a similar meaning is "habs," which also signifies "stop" or "withhold." Scholars in Islamic jurisprudence (fiqh) unanimously concur that linguistically, the definition of "waqf" aligns closely with the term "al-habs," as it more accurately reflects the concept in Sharia law (JAWHAR,2021)

Moreover, Al-Qur'an establishes a strong basis for promoting the institution of Waqf through verses discussing the concept of almsgiving. This practice is closely linked to the objective of drawing nearer to Allah SWT (taqarrub) and engaging in benevolent actions, ultimately aiming to attain the promised rewards from Allah SWT in the Hereafter. *"Who is the person who (wants) to give a loan to Allah, as a good loan (sincere) so that Allah multiplies his reward by doubling the amount? Remember that Allah is the One who narrows and expands (the provision) and to Him you will all be returned"* (Surah al-Baqarah 2: 245).

Numerous hadiths highlight that Prophet Muhammad (SAW) advocated for the establishment of Waqf and actively engaged in it, serving as a prominent example for his companions and the Muslim community. One of the well-known hadiths, narrated by Abu Hurairah (RA), underscores the Prophet's commitment to Waqf, stating:

"When the son of Adam dies, his deeds come to an end except for three things: Sadaqah Jariyah (continuous charity), A knowledge which gives benefit, or a righteous child who prays for him (the deceased)." (Narrated by Muslim).

According to scholars, the interpretation of sadaqah jariyah in the mentioned hadith aligns with the practice of Waqf, which Islam strongly endorses. This practice has the potential to yield continuous and enduring rewards for the Waqf as long as the waqf property remains permanently available for use by the designated recipient (marque 'alaih), whether it involves a general or specific waqf. The fundamental idea behind the execution of Waqf during the era of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) and his companions is evident in the hadith narrated by Ibn 'Umar, as documented by Muslims. Seeking guidance, Ibn 'Umar recounts that his father, 'Umar al-Khattab, procured a piece of land in Khaybar. He promptly approached the Prophet Muhammad (SAW) for advice on utilizing the land.

"You can keep the property if you like, but donate its income". According to Ibn' Umar: "The land is not sold, not made an inheritance (not inherited) and not transferred to another person (hibah). All the produce of the land was distributed to people experiencing poverty, the family, my servants, fisabilillah, ibn sabil, and to support the guests. It is not an offence for the trustee of the waqf land to take reasonable proceeds of the waqf land to cover his livelihood or to treat the guests, as long as do not turn them into one's private property" (Narrated by Muslim)

The term "waqf" does not directly appear in the Qur'an or hadith. It has evolved through the interpretations of jurists, stemming from the practice of sadaqah jariah, also known as al-sadaqah al-muharramah. Its Implementation aims to benefit heirs or serve the common good. Fiqh scholars hold varying perspectives on defining Waqf due to limited and general references in the Qur'an and hadith. Consequently, differences in opinion among jurists are expected, shaped by their experiences and the influence of local communities during debates on this subject.

Waqf, according to Mazhab Maliki

Waqf is defined as withholding benefits from ownership, where the property remains under the ownership of the waqif while being designated for charitable purposes. In this perspective, if an individual donates a piece of land, tamar trees, or a house to the poor through Waqf, they retain the right to manage the property, whether through rent or distribution to the poor, until their death. If the waqif decides to distribute the waqf property among their heirs, it ceases to be considered Waqf and becomes part of the inheritance. Notably, the Maliki School does not impose the condition of permanence or ta'bid for accepting Waqf, even in the case of a mosque waqf.

Waqf, according Mazhab Hanafi

According to Abu Hanifah, Waqf involves the detention of property ('ayn) belonging to another party to derive benefits for charitable purposes immediately or in the future. In this context, the control of waqf property remains with the waqif, and the act of Waqf does not transfer ownership permanently since it is considered a non-binding transaction (ghayr lazim). This places Waqf in a category similar to the concept of borrowing ('ariyah), which is also non-binding. Abu Hanifah specified that his ownership would cease upon a judge declaring the property as Waqf or the waqif's death.

This perspective contrasts with Abu Yusuf's view, which believes that Waqf can occur solely through verbal intent. On the other hand, Muhammad holds that the transfer of property rights occurs after handing it over to the party responsible for its management.

Waqf, according to Mazhab Shafi'i

According to the Shafi'i school, Waqf is characterized by the permanent detention of property, allowing its utilization while depriving the owner of their ownership rights. The property is employed for charitable purposes, serving as a means for individuals to draw closer to Allah SWT. Imam al-Sharbini defines Waqf as the withholding of property that retains its form and usability, with the generated proceeds directed toward the intended purpose, as determined by the waqif according to Shariah. Notably, the original property has not been relinquished.

In the Shafi'i perspective, it is deemed haram for a waqif to retain permanent possession of waqf property. However, the waqif can be appointed as the manager of the waqf property, granting the right to distribute the proceeds. Unless explicitly stated by the waqif that they, or their other heirs, can use and benefit from the property, the waqif cannot access the proceeds, as they have fully surrendered their right by dedicating it exclusively to Allah SWT.

Waqf according Mazhab Hambali

According to Ibn Qudamah, Waqf involves retaining ownership of a property while directing its proceeds towards the path of Allah SWT. Al-Bahuti further defines Waqf as the waqif or their representative retaining rights to a beneficial property, even though ownership no longer belongs to them. Unlike a contractual agreement, Waqf does not involve an exchange but instead suspends property rights to draw closer to Allah SWT.

The waqif is generally not permitted to benefit from what has been waqf, except when specified in the waqf terms, allowing them to receive benefits based on an allocated portion. Alternatively, exceptions may apply in cases where the endowed property is designated for general use, such as in the case of Waqf for mosques, cemeteries, and similar purposes.

Water Crisis Overview

Water is a fundamental necessity for all of humanity and the entire world. Out of the Earth's entire surface, 70% is covered by water. Allah SWT has designated water as a crucial medium for humans to sustain life and enable them to worship Him. One of the Islamic charities that must be strengthened to serve the needs of the populace better is Waqf. For ages, the community has been aware of and engaged in Waqf, a type of mu'amalah māliyah. Early Islamic Waqf was restricted to the place and requirements of worship; however, it later evolved into various forms and uses that positively responded to societal needs as times changed. Examples of these include special Waqf for aiding the underprivileged and travellers, hotel waqf, jewellery waqf, wedding equipment waqf, health waqf, and Waqf for agricultural land and water resources (Kurniawan & Mohiddin, 2021).

The world has long struggled with inadequate clean water and sanitary services. Access to water and sanitary facilities is crucial to improve someone's health. It takes a significant financial outlay to finance purified water and sanitary services. Currently, 633 million people worldwide lack access to clean, well-maintained sanitation facilities and treated water. Geographical variables, disorganized population settlement, scarce financial resources, and frequently shifting government politics are the causes of this. Poor nations, mainly growing Islamic nations like Sudan, Yemen, Qatar, Lebanon, and other Western Asia, frequently experience this absence of difficulties. This is brought on by unstable internal political issues, sparse population density, non-strategic geographic location, and restricted revenue streams. Extreme poverty brought on by a shortage of natural resources is the primary cause of this limitation (Roslan et al, 2023).

UNDP (2015) estimates that the allocation to provide comprehensive access to water services and sanitation facilities by the year 2030 would be around US\$27 billion annually. This is expected to pose various constraints, particularly for low-income countries.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

SDGs stands for Sustainable Development Goals. The Sustainable Development Goals are 17 global goals established by the United Nations in 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The goals are designed to address a range of global challenges and guide efforts toward a more sustainable, equitable, and inclusive future by 2030. Besides that, the 17 SDGs cover a broad spectrum of issues, including poverty, hunger, health, education, gender equality, clean water, sanitation, affordable and clean energy, climate action, and more. The goals are interconnected and aim to tackle complex and interrelated challenges facing the world today.

Also, SDGs provide a framework for international cooperation, policy development, and collective action to promote sustainable development and improve the well-being of people and the planet. They are intended to be universal, applying to all countries, regardless of their level of development, and involve a commitment to leaving no one behind. Progress toward achieving the SDGs is monitored globally, and efforts are made to mobilize resources and partnerships to accelerate advancements toward these goals.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were created by the United Nations. The development of the SDGs was a collaborative and inclusive process that involved member states, international organizations, civil society, and various stakeholders. The United Nations General Assembly officially adopted the goals in September 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. The 17 goals and associated targets address a wide range of global challenges, promoting social, economic, and environmental sustainability. The SDGs build on the earlier Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and represent a comprehensive and integrated framework for addressing the world's most pressing issues.

In addition, The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), as outlined on the official SDGs website, encompass 169 targets, each specific to one of the 17 overarching goals. These targets serve as measurable objectives guiding global efforts toward sustainable development. The reported 3879 events signify a multitude of activities and gatherings conducted on a global scale to raise awareness, foster collaboration, and drive action in support of the SDGs. Additionally, the recorded 1348 publications reflect the wealth of official documents, guidelines, and reports dedicated to providing information and tracking progress related to the SDGs. The substantial figure of 7805 actions indicates a broad spectrum of initiatives and efforts undertaken worldwide to align with and contribute to achieving the SDG targets. Together, these numbers underscore the comprehensive and dynamic nature of the SDGs, highlighting the global community's commitment to advancing sustainable development through a multitude of events, publications, and actions.

SDG	GOAL	Description
1	No Poverty	End poverty in all its forms everywhere.
2	Zero Hunger	End hunger, achieve food security, and promote sustainable agriculture.
3	Good Health and Well-being	Ensure healthy lives and promote well-being for all at all ages.
4	Quality Education	Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning.
5	Gender Equality	Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls.
6	Clean Water and Sanitation	Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all.
7	Affordable and Clean Energy	Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all.
8	Decent Work and Economic Growth	Promote sustained, inclusive, sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work.
9	Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure	Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization, and foster innovation.
10	Reduced Inequality	Reduce inequality within and among countries.
11	Sustainable Cities and Communities	Make cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable.
12	Responsible Consumption and Production	Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns.
13	Climate Action	Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts.
14	Life Below Water	Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and marine resources for sustainable development.
15	Life on Land	Protect, restore, and promote sustainable use of terrestrial ecosystems, sustainably manage forests, combat desertification, and halt and reverse land degradation and biodiversity loss.
16	Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions	Promote peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, provide access to justice for all, and build effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions at all levels.
17	Partnerships for the Goals	Strengthen the means of Implementation and revitalize the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development.

Abdullah (2018) observed that most of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) align seamlessly with Shariah's long-term objectives. The study suggests a significant opportunity for stakeholders in Awqaf to

formulate a development plan grounded in waqf principles that correspond to the SDGs framework. Furthermore, the research indicates that global awqaf possesses substantial financial resources, presenting the potential to assist Muslim-majority countries in promptly achieving particular highly pertinent and pressing maqasid-oriented SDGs.

Sustainable economic development rooted in Islamic principles extends beyond economic factors, encompassing comprehensive attributes such as social, moral, material, and spiritual dimensions. Essentially, it is intricately linked to enhancing individuals' living standards (Muliadi, 2020). Islamic social finance (ISF) instruments, including Waqf, have been pivotal in fostering socioeconomic development and alleviating poverty for more than 1,400 years. In Islamic history, Waqf has been a significant provider of social services, many currently funded by the state.

In the realm of Islamic Finance, Malaysia continues to be a trailblazer, leading innovations in the waqf sector. Numerous Islamic financial institutions (IFIs) in the country have actively explored various forms of Waqf, aligning with different Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and resulting in a diverse waqf landscape:

1. **Cash Waqf:** Malaysia authorized cash waqf through a national fatwa in 2007, recognizing its broader donor base and affordability compared to property. The Malaysia Waqaf Foundation (Yayasan Waqaf Malaysia) utilizes cash endowments to transform waqf land into productive assets like hotels and the Terengganu Culinary Academy (contributing to SDG 1: No Poverty and SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth). Recently, eight banks collaborated on the 'mywakaf' digital platform, allowing the public to contribute cash waqf to various socioeconomic projects.
2. **Corporate Waqf:** Johor Corporation (JCorp) pioneered corporate Waqf in Malaysia by donating 12.35 million shares of its publicly listed subsidiaries, valued at RM200 million. Waqaf An-Nur Corporation, a JCorp subsidiary, manages several waqf medical facilities, contributing to SDG 3: Good Health and Well-Being.
3. **Microfinance:** In 2021, Malaysia's central bank, Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM), incorporated cash waqf as a funding source for its iTEKAD program. iTEKAD, a collaborative effort with Islamic banks, provides seed capital, microfinancing, and training to microentrepreneurs, aligning with SDG 1: No Poverty, SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, and SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities.
4. **Waqf Shares:** Malaysia introduced the world's first waqf initial public offering in 2015. Waqaf An-Nur offered 85 million shares, with proceeds used to upgrade the Larkin Sentral Terminal and assist low-income, single mothers with rent payments at the transport hub's shop lots (contributing to SDG 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure and SDG 10: Reduced Inequalities).
5. **Waqf Boat Initiative:** The waqf authorities in the state of Perak provide boats and equipment to fishermen, contributing to Malaysia's blue economy and addressing SDG 1: No Poverty and SDG 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth.

METHODOLOGY

The method used in this paper is descriptive qualitative. The discussion is focused on providing a descriptive explanation of the relationship between Islamic social finance and the SDGs. Furthermore, the discussion is continued by a conceptual framework that explains the role of Islamic social finance in encouraging the achievement of the SDGs. In the writing of this paper, the researcher refers to reference materials through journal articles, government documents, and online newspapers from various fields such as Waqf and Quranic verses. This working paper will present the proposed Cash Waqf model by the Malaysian Waqf Foundation in seeking funds utilizing them for better and comprehensive services.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

According to statistics from the National Water Services Commission (SPAN), Malaysians, on average, use 201 liters of water per person per day, equivalent to 134 bottles of 1.5 liters each. This surpasses the recommendation set by the United Nations (UN), which suggests a daily consumption of 165 litres of water per individual (Murninets2.0,2024).

Waqf stands as an Islamic social financial instrument, offering sustainability advantages. Initiatives to generate waqf assets are geared towards maximizing their utilization to achieve a more equitable distribution across various facets. Kahf (1998) characterizes Waqf as a tool for ensuring security through distribution and benefit-sharing for the benefit of people experiencing poverty, akin to zakat instruments. This demonstrates that Waqf plays a significant role in the socioeconomic development of communities, including areas such as education, health, infrastructure, shelters, and more. Cash waqf provides a broader avenue for a diverse range of donors to participate in philanthropic endeavors and attain perpetual rewards compared to Waqf limited to immovable property. While not everyone can afford to endow a piece of land, nearly anyone can contribute to a cash waqf.

Details of the Malaysian Cash Waqf Collection:

1. Malaysian Cash Waqf System
2. Cash Waqf Counter & Postal Order
3. Internet Banking
4. Salary Deduction
5. Takaful Contributions & Grants
6. Bank Deposits
7. Bank Grants (Hibah)
8. Income Fund generated by Yayasan Waqaf Malaysia)

The Cash Waqf Water Services is a special waqf product established under the Malaysian Cash Waqf through the collaboration of the Yayasan Waqaf Malaysia (YWM) and the Ministry of Environment and Water (KASA). As of December 2023, the total collection amounted to RM4,560,738.61. The total distribution was RM3,577,860.98, leaving a current balance of RM982,877.63 Yayasan Waqaf Malaysia. (2024)

NEGERI	PROJECTS	RINGGIT (RM)
KEDAH	21	RM877,464.00
KELANTAN	16	RM736,081.00
SARAWAK	9	RM611,952.00
PAHANG	11	RM571,805.00
SABAH	4	RM286,109.00
PERAK	5	RM181,655.00
SELANGOR	4	RM120,653.98
NEGERI SEMBILAN	3	RM109,685.00
JOHOR	2	RM109,865.00

The Cash Water Waqaf aims to collect waqf funds to finance small-scale water service projects valued at less than RM50,000 on the Peninsular Malaysia and RM75,000 for Sabah and Sarawak, including

- a. Implementation of water source tapping systems from wells;
- b. Purchase of replacement equipment, one-time maintenance;
- c. Operational aid funds for the prevention and recovery of rural water supply systems; and
- d. Provision of alternative water sources involving low-maintenance and safe-to-use costs

The funds allocated to water waqf projects are utilized to construct and maintain essential infrastructure such as wells, water treatment facilities, and distribution networks. Water waqf initiatives strive to alleviate water scarcity, enhance public health, and uplift living standards by focusing on the perpetual benefit and community welfare principles inherent in Islamic Finance. The collaborative nature of these projects often involves partnerships with government authorities, water management agencies, and local communities to ensure effective planning, execution, and long-term sustainability.

Water waqf initiatives may also include educational programs to promote responsible water usage and hygiene practices, fostering a comprehensive approach to water resource management. Ultimately, Islamic Waqf on water supply embodies the principles of social responsibility, philanthropy, and sustainability, contributing to the well-being and development of communities in alignment with Islamic values.

Figure 1: Distribution Waqf Fund (Malaysian Cash Waqf)

Dana *Taslim*, derived from contributions to the Malaysian Cash Waqf, is designated for two specific purposes. Firstly, the fund is directed towards acquiring permanent assets through Purchase or construction. Secondly, during the interim period until replaced by permanent assets, the fund is invested in Sharia-compliant investment products with a capital guarantee. The returns from these investments are then returned to Dana Taslim to preserve the initial value of the fund. These funds serve the common objectives of supporting religious, educational, housing, food, and health initiatives.

'Dana *Tawzi*' is more flexible as it can be utilized to develop waqf projects or charitable contributions that are non-permanent. This fund is accumulated through:

1. Returns obtained from completed development projects.
2. Profits from investments.
3. Gains derived from Dana Tawzi itself.

The versatility of Dana Tawzi' allows it to support various initiatives, contributing to the betterment of society through both development projects and charitable endeavours. The fund is replenished through returns, profits, and gains, ensuring a continuous support cycle for impactful and sustainable projects."

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Incorporating Waqf and Zakat into the financial sector can significantly contribute to achieving SDGs, including mitigating the vulnerability of impoverished communities and advancing the education and health sectors. However, SDGs can be matched with Islamic principles, and the few concerns contradicting Shariah, such as gender equality, do not invalidate the SDGs' value proposition as a viable framework for sustainable development. In advancing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) within the socioeconomic landscape of Malaysia, philanthropic instruments such as *Waqf*, *zakat*, and *sadaqah* are poised to play a pivotal role. Their inherent potential to foster collaboration solidarity and provide alternative financial mechanisms

positions them as influential tools for the nation's pursuit of sustainable development objectives. The Malaysian Waqf Foundation model has successfully assisted the Malaysian community in accessing water. Economically challenged Islamic nations should consider this model to enable their communities to lead better lives. For recommendation to actively pursue harmonization initiatives in Majlis Agama Negeri, Islamic Finance Institutions and Yayasan Waqf Malaysia to foster clarity, consistency, and enhanced integration between Shariah rulings, national laws, and SDGs in Malaysia.

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